

IDENTIFICATION OF THE LOCAL STIFFNESS REDUCTION OF A DAMAGED COMPOSITE PLATE USING THE VIRTUAL FIELDS METHOD

J.-H.Kim^a, F. Pierron^a, M. Wisnom^b

^a: LMPF, Arts et Métiers ParisTech

Rue St Dominique, BP 508, 51000 Châlons en Champagne, France

^b: Advanced Composites Centre for Innovation and Science, University of Bristol

Queen's Building, University Walk, BS8 1TR Bristol, UK

jin.kim@chalons.ensam.fr – fabrice.pierron@chalons.ensam.fr –

m.wisnom@bristol.ac.uk

SUMMARY

The virtual fields method (VFM) is used as an inverse procedure to process curvatures obtained from full-field measurements for the identification of the local loss of stiffness in composite plates. The method not only picks up the location of the damage but also provides a fairly good estimate of the stiffness reduction in the damaged area.

Keywords: Virtual Fields Method, Full-field measurement, Local stiffness reduction, Damage detection

INTRODUCTION

Composite panels are prone to delamination damage caused by impact or faulty manufacturing process. This results in a local loss of stiffness in the panel where the delamination has occurred, which may cause premature failure of the components, particularly in compression because of local buckling effects. The present study aims at taking advantage of the availability of non-contact full-field measurements and adapted inverse identification procedures in order to not only locate the damage but also identify the local stiffness reduction of the panel. To do so, full-field heterogeneous slope fields are measured through a deflectometry technique. The interest of slope compared to deflection is that only one differentiation is required to obtain the curvatures which directly relate to the strains in the framework of Kirchhoff thin plate theory. In this study, the virtual fields method (VFM) [1] is used as an inverse procedure to process curvatures for the identification of the local loss of stiffness. The VFM is based on a relevant use of the equilibrium equations through the principle of virtual work. The stiffness components can be determined directly from the VFM when the material is homogeneous, however, the VFM should be adapted to the case of a plate with stiffnesses varying spatially.

METHODOLOGY

Deflectometry

In this study, deflectometry [2] was chosen as the full-field measurement technique since it gives direct access to slopes, as opposed to deflection measurements by stereo image correlation, for instance. The principle of deflectometry was discussed in detail in [2, 3]. The original deflectometry setup is shown in Fig. 1 (a).

Figure 1. Camera position in deflectometry (a) behind the grid (b) beside the grid

The relation between the spatial phase difference $d\varphi$ and the slope variation $d\alpha$ can be derived as:

$$d\varphi = 2\pi \frac{u}{p} = 2\pi \frac{2hd\alpha(1 + \tan^2(\theta))}{p} = \frac{4\pi h}{p} d\alpha(1 + \tan^2(\theta)) \quad (1)$$

where p is the pitch of the reference grid and h the distance between the plate and the grid. The sensitivity s is the ratio between the measured phase and the slope. If h is reasonably large compared with the tested plate, then $\tan^2(\theta)$ can be neglected with respect to 1.

Data Processing

A first image of the plate at rest is taken. A phase map is computed from the obtained grid intensity field with the windowed discrete Fourier transform (WDFT) algorithm implemented in the Frangyne software (see www.techlab.fr). Then, the plate is deformed and another phase field is computed. Phase subtraction of the deformed phase map from the undeformed one produces a wrapped phase map. The wrapped phase map is unwrapped (demodulation) using an unwrapping algorithm in the same software. These unwrapped phase maps are then converted to slope data by means of the sensitivity. The three curvature components are then obtained from the two measured slope fields by numerical differentiation. Because differentiation is very sensitive to spatial noise, it is necessary to apply some spatial smoothing. The slope maps are fitted by polynomials before differentiation using a linear least-square method. However, this

process inevitably causes loss of spatial resolution. Since local damage induces local stress and strain redistribution, the spatial resolution is very important in investigating the local fields. The best solution to avoid the loss of spatial resolution is to perform direct differentiation without smoothing. Thanks to the high sensitivity and resolution of the deflectometry technique, the curvature fields can be obtained here without spatial smoothing. In the case of direct differentiation without smoothing, the original geometrical set-up (Fig. 1 (a)) cannot be used due to the missing data of reflected hole area. Thus, a new geometrical set-up is required, which can avoid the hole image. For this purpose, the camera is located beside the grid (Fig. 1 (b)) instead of behind the grid (Fig. 1 (a)). In the set-up represented in Fig. 1 (a), the value of $\tan^2(\theta)$ in Eq. 1 is negligible with respect to 1, but in the new configuration, the value should be included in the calculation of sensitivity as the value of $\tan^2(\theta)$ increases.

The Virtual Fields Method

In the case of thin orthotropic plates in pure static bending, if body forces are neglected, the equilibrium equation of the principle of virtual work can be written as:

$$\int_S D_{11} \kappa_1 \kappa_1^* dS + \int_S D_{12} (\kappa_1 \kappa_2^* + \kappa_2 \kappa_1^*) dS + \int_S D_{22} \kappa_2 \kappa_2^* dS + \int_S D_{66} \kappa_6 \kappa_6^* dS = \sum_{j=1}^n F_j w_j^* \quad (2)$$

where

- S: surface of the plate
- w^* : virtual deflection field
- F: normal forces applied to the plate at n points
- κ : actual curvature fields
- κ^* : virtual curvature fields derived from w^*
- D_{ij} : bending stiffness components

It is worth noting that the VFM utilizes the kinematic assumptions of plate theories in plate bending, since strain fields cannot be obtained from inside the specimen. In this study, the Kirchhoff plate kinematic assumption of linear through-the-thickness displacement distributions is adopted. When the material is homogeneous, the stiffness components can be moved outside of the integration sign and the choice of a particular set of virtual fields will provide a linear system relating the unknown stiffnesses to the external forces (measured by the load cell), geometrical parameters and weighted integrals of the actual curvatures that can be computed provided that full-field measurements are available. The key issue of the VFM is the choice of appropriate virtual fields among the infinite possibilities. Recently, with the development of the so-called special virtual fields [1] and the optimization of these special fields with respect to noise sensitivity [4], this problem has been solved efficiently. These methods have established an automatic procedure for virtual fields selection. However, when the plate

has stiffnesses that vary with the in-plane space variables x and y , the D stiffness components cannot be moved outside the integrals in Eq. 2. It is then necessary to find some ‘parameterization’ to solve the problem. To describe the variation of the stiffness with the space variables, a continuous approach was chosen. The use of polynomials is considered in this approach, which will have the performance of high sensitivity to the stiffness reduction but poor spatial resolution owing to the nature of polynomials. In this case, the damage was supposed isotropic, *i.e.*, all the stiffness components were reduced by the same quantity, therefore the number of unknowns was kept relatively low by using the following parameterization:

$$\tilde{D} = D^0 \{1 + p(x/L, y/W)\} \quad (3)$$

where \tilde{D} is the bending stiffness tensor of the damaged plate, D^0 is that of the virgin material and p is a polynomial function of the normalized in-plane coordinates x/L and y/W , where L is the length and W the width of the panel. This polynomial can be interpreted as a stiffness reduction coefficient. The virtual fields method can be adapted to identify the coefficients of the polynomial, provided that the undamaged stiffnesses are known. The detailed procedure is described in [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact damage is important in composite laminates, and involves significant delamination. Two types of delamination in different through-thickness positions will be examined. The first type is a delamination located near the surface, which generally induces a local bulge zone, and the second is a delamination at the mid-plane. The last verification performed in the present study concerns real impact damage.

Near-the-surface delamination

The first experimental validation was to identify the local stiffness reduction of a near-the-surface delamination having a bulge zone. Delaminations are usually generated between the layers with different fibre orientations, not between the layers with the same lay-up angle. In order to investigate realistically the effect of delamination, a cross-ply THR160/EH84 carbon epoxy laminated plate was fabricated. The material properties are $E_{11}=105\text{GPa}$, $E_{22}=9.5\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=4.4\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12}=0.32$. The plate size is $150 \times 120 \text{ mm}^2$ and its thickness is 2.5 mm with a $[0/90]_{4s}$ layup. A $40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ size FEP release film was inserted into the two interfaces between the 1st - 2nd and 2nd - 3rd plies during fabrication of the laminate to create the near-the-surface delamination (8.9% relative area of damage). After curing the laminates, bulging (*i.e.* the surface was not flat) was observed on the area of the surface where the FEP release film was inserted (back surface). As the surface of a composite plate is not naturally reflective enough to be used for deflectometry, surface preparation is necessary. A special thin resin coating (gel coat) was applied to the top surface to make it specular (mirror-like). The experimental implementation was performed using the deflectometry set-up shown in Fig. 2. A 2272×1704 pixels CCD camera observes the specimen surface and a light

illuminates the reference grid. The pitch of the reference grid is 2 mm. The distance h between the plate surface and the grid was measured with a metallic tape, giving $h=1333 \pm 1$ mm. The composite plate is supported by specially designed point grips to give simple support conditions and the load is applied by a load sensor developed in-house. The plate was tested in bending according to the load configuration in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Deflectometry set-up.

Figure 3. Geometry and test configuration of the damaged plate

This load configuration will be used for the rest of the experiments. The applied load was 15 N. Two camera positions (*i.e.* central and offset) in the deflectometry were used in order to investigate the effect of camera position on the identification results. The same experimental conditions were used except the camera position. As discussed previously, the offset deflectometry configuration (see Fig. 1 (b)) requires a calibration for the camera position. The results of local stiffness reduction detection on the near-the-surface delamination are shown in Fig. 4. Either piecewise or polynomial virtual fields have been used in the past and in the present case, there is not much difference between the two. Polynomial virtual fields have been selected for the present study. 8th order polynomial parameterization was used for the damage polynomial, as in [3], giving a total number of unknowns of 44. On the plots, the red color indicates no stiffness reduction (*i.e.*, no damage) and the blue, a reduction of stiffness (damage), with the magnitude of the stiffness reduction on the color bar. The damage zone is correctly located and with a stiffness reduction corresponding to expectations (about 30%,

assuming zero stiffness in the delaminated plies due to the bulging) in both cases. The identified location from the offset camera position experiment is more accurate than that of the original camera position one. It can therefore be said that the reconstruction of the missing data (hole image), which in this case is close to the damage zone, has a significant impact on the damage location and that camera offset is preferable.

Figure 4. Identification of the stiffness reduction on the near-the-surface delamination with (a) original camera position including exact damaged area and (b) offset camera position including exact damaged area.

Mid-plane Delamination

The next experimental verification performed in the present study concerns the stiffness reduction for a mid-plane delamination. For the experiments, a UD THR160/EH84 carbon epoxy laminated plate with an embedded mid-plane delamination was fabricated. The plate size is $150 \times 120 \text{ mm}^2$ and its thickness is 2.5 mm with 16 layers of prepreg. A double layer of FEP release film with a size of $40 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ was inserted into the mid-plane during lay-up. The experimental implementation was performed using the offset camera position. The applied load was 15N. In this study, for efficient FE modelling, a sublaminated model utilizing two thin shell finite elements through-the-thickness direction was used to model the offsets (*i.e.* kinematic discontinuity due to delamination) between the separated sublaminates. Each sublaminated is connected by rigid bar elements to represent the undamaged laminate with the removal of these connecting elements simulating the delamination damage. In order to validate the proposed FE model, the three curvature components from the experimental measurements were compared with those from the FEA. The curvature fields are shown in Fig. 5. It is observed that the simulated curvatures (Fig. 5 (a)) are in good agreement with the experimental ones (Fig. 5 (b)) (the same scale is used to represent both results). It is considered that the current FE model describes accurately the characteristic of mid-plane delamination owing to the geometrical offset (kinematic discontinuity over the delaminated area) used in the FE model. From the experimental measurements (Fig. 5 (b)), the local curvature variations due to the stress concentration at the ends of the delamination can be observed clearly thanks to the high spatial resolution. Thanks to the availability of the full-field measurement technique, the strain distribution in the presence of delamination can be investigated more thoroughly and the proposed FE model was validated efficiently. The detection results of local stiffness reduction for the

mid-plane delamination are shown in Fig. 6. 8th order polynomial parameterization was used. Since the second moment of area (I) decreases with the third power of thickness, much higher bending stiffness reduction was expected. Unexpected results were observed, however, both in location and stiffness reduction. The damage zone is not correctly located and the detected damage zone is elongated in the vertical direction.

Figure 5. Comparison of curvature fields between (a) FEA and (b) the experiment.

Figure 6. Comparison of stiffness reduction results between (a) experiment, and (b) FEA.

Despite the strong effect on the curvature field of the mid-plane delamination, the stiffness reduction is less than that of the near-surface delamination. In the original scale, the exact location of delamination is shown. Strange behaviour showing apparent stiffness reduction on the right hand side of delamination and stiffness increase on the left hand side can be seen. In order to analyze the unexpected behaviour and the characteristics of the mid-plane delamination, the stress distributions (in the x direction) in the top layer between the mid-plane delamination and other types of damage are compared using FE simulation in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Comparison of stress fields in the x direction on the top surface between several damage types (FEA, BSR: bending stiffness reduction).

For the mid-plane delamination, the sublaminates model was used, and for other types of damage, a property degradation model which substitutes the damaged material with an equivalent material of reduced elastic properties was used (BSR). The size of the plate is $190 \times 140 \text{ mm}^2$, with a nominal damaged area of $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$. The applied load was 10 N. A detailed stress analysis revealed that the stress field due to mid-plane delamination is significantly different from that due to other damage types. In the damage having bending stiffness reduction, the stress level over the damage zone is higher than that of the same area in the undamaged plate. If the reduction of bending stiffness increases, also the stress level increases. On the contrary, in the case of mid-plane delamination, a stress anomaly is observed on the left hand side of the delamination area. The stress reversal (negative stress) on the left hand side of the mid-plane delamination is a very specific feature. At this stage, it is worth considering how the VFM recognizes the stiffness reduction, more exactly stiffness variation. When there is a localized damage in a composite laminated plate, the damage induces a reduction of local stiffness. The reduced local stiffness will redistribute the stress fields around the damaged area. Since the VFM utilizes the global equilibrium of a given specimen having specific force and boundary conditions, it can examine the stress fields

all over the specimen. Consequently, it can recognize any abnormal state of stress due to the damage using the given geometry, loading, and boundary conditions. In the case of mid-plane delamination, the VFM recognizes the higher stress as a stiffness reduction and the abnormal lower stress as a stiffness increase. On the damage map (see Fig. 6), one can see a stiffness reduction on the right hand side of the delamination, and a stiffness increase on the left hand side due to the stress reversal. The current methodology with the adapted VFM utilizes the Kirchhoff plate kinematic assumption of linear through-the-thickness displacement distributions. In the case of a mid-plane delamination (kinematic discontinuity), this kinematic assumption is no longer valid. Consequently, the current methodology has shown unsatisfactory identification for the case of mid-plane delamination. It was observed that if the damage does not violate the kinematic assumption, it can be identified with the current methodology in a satisfactory manner. Conversely, if the through-the-thickness displacement distribution is significantly different from linear, then the current methodology cannot yield a correct identification. It is considered that however, in real impact damage, the delaminations will be distributed through-the-thickness and the through-the-thickness displacement would be more linear. This will have to be validated in the future.

Impact Damage

The last experimental verification performed in the present study is on real impact damage. A low velocity impact test was carried out on a cross-ply THR160/EH84 carbon epoxy laminated plate using a drop weight method. The plate size is $150 \times 120 \text{ mm}^2$ and its thickness is 2.5 mm with a $[0/90]_{4s}$ layup. A drop weight impactor with a spherical steel ball end of 28 mm diameter was used for the impact test. The plate was fixed on all four sides by a fixture and the impact was applied directly to the plate. The impactor, with a total mass of 10 kg, was dropped from a distance of 20 cm above the specimen. The applied impact energy was about 20 J and the impact speed was 2 m/s, calculated from the potential energy. Barely visible impact damage (BVID) was observed on the surface of the specimen. A small dent was found on the impacted side and a small bulging due to delamination on the opposite side of impact. The experimental implementation was performed according to the offset camera configuration. The applied load was 15 N. The identification result of local stiffness reduction on the impacted plate is shown in Fig. 8. 8th order polynomial parameterization was used. It is observed that stiffness reduction in this case is less than 10%. Despite the very small damage area and the low stiffness contrast, the damage zone is reasonably located and the elliptical form is retrieved. The C-scan image of the impact damage is shown in Fig. 9. This suggests that in a real impact damage, the delaminations will be distributed through-the-thickness and the problems encountered with a single mid-plane delamination will be less relevant. This will obviously have to be confirmed on a full study on real impacted plates with damage observation. It would be very useful to have some better quantification of the damage by de-plying, cutting, and observing under a microscope or using a CT scan. Then, a judgement could be made about whether the 10% reduction detected is reasonable. It should be noted however that a stiffness contrast physically corresponds to local strain gradients. Indeed, a 10% stiffness variation corresponds to a local strain shift of the order of 10% of the local strain. This explains why such stiffness contrasts are so difficult to obtain and so

sensitive to noise. The effect one has to detect here is one order of magnitude below the main effect (global bending of the plate). It is therefore very satisfactory that such a small effect can be detected here. This is due to both the quality of the measurements (deflectometry is very sensitive) and the polynomial parameterization of the damage distribution which provides the required amount of spatial smoothing.

Figure 8. Identification of the stiffness reduction on the impact damage (a) with original scale (including exact location of impact damage, the location of the bulge zone was measured with a tape measure) and (b) with adjusted scale.

Figure 9. C-scan image of the impact damage.

References

1. Grédiac M, Toussaint E, and Pierron F. Special virtual fields for the direct determination of material parameters with the virtual fields method. 1- Principle and definition. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 39(10):2691-2705, 2002.
2. Surrel Y. Deflectometry: a simple and efficient noninterferometric method for slope measurement. In *Xth SEM International Congress on Experimental Mechanics*, 2004.
3. Kim J-H, Pierron F, Wisnom MR, and Syed-Muhamad K. Identification of the local stiffness reduction of a damaged composite plate using the virtual fields method. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 38(9):2065-2075, 2007.
4. Avril S, Grédiac M, and Pierron F. Sensitivity of the virtual fields method to noisy data. *Computational Mechanics*, 34(6):439-452, 2004.